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LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences is a multi-disciplinary journal published by the Lagos State University, Nigeria. Its major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

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CONTENTS

THEORETICAL MODELS FOR ENHANCING OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY IN NIGERIAN BUSINESSES	
Anwuli Nkemchor Obiki-Osafiele, Olajide Soji Osundare, Edith Ebele Agu & Ibrahim Adedeji Adeniran	1
EFFECT OF TALENT RETENTION ON PERFORMANCE OF NNPC DOWNSTREAM OIL SECTOR IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA	
Onyekuru Akudo, Nnadi-Nicholas Eucharua Obiageri & Prof. G. A. Emerole	20
PUSH AND PULL MOTIVATION FACTORS: A PANACEA FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CHALLENGES IN OLUMINRIN WATERFALLS, NIGERIA	
Folusade Arowosafe & Oyebola Akinwotu	30
TALENT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND SALES PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN UMUAHIA, ABIA STATE, NIGERIA	
Chinaza Olive Jacob, Victor Monday Dibie (PhD.) & Chinwe Obiora Onuba (PhD.)	41
MAKING USE OF OPERATIONS RESEARCH TECHNIQUES IN NIGERIAN BUSINESS ORGANIZATIONS	
Ighomereho, O. Salome	58
EFFECT OF SUCCESSION PLANNING ON ORGANIZATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN SOUTH-SOUTH	
Okon, Nse Bassey, J. C. Ihemeje (PhD.) & S. M. Okebaram (PhD.)	76
ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND SALES PERFORMANCE	
Victor Rupert Otu, Victor Monday Dibie (PhD.) & Emmanuel Linus Unanam	89
EFFECT OF CYBERSECURITY ON BUSINESS MODEL INNOVATION IN SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES (SMEs) IN ABIA STATE	
Ufomba, Rex Eze (PhD.); Awusa, Peter Ewa (PhD.) & Ochi-agbajeogu, Evelyn Nwamaka (PhD.)	102
ECONOMIC COMMUNITY OF WEST AFRICAN STATE (ECOWAS) PROTOCOL ON SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIALIZATION IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA	
Hussaina Adamu Mohammed, Abdullahi Mohammed Abdul & Musa Ibrahim Aliyu (PhD.)	114
ASSESSMENT OF BORDER SECURITY MANAGEMENT AND ECOWAS PROTOCOL ON FREE MOVEMENT OF PERSONS AND GOODS	
Haruna Ali-Gombe, Caleb Ruth Luka (PhD.) & Aminu Ibrahim (PhD.)	130

ASSESSMENT OF BORDER SECURITY MANAGEMENT AND ECOWAS PROTOCOL ON FREE MOVEMENT OF PERSONS AND GOODS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the implementation of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons and Goods and its implications for trans-border security threats in Nigeria, using Border regimes Theory as its theoretical framework. The research critically examines the mechanisms established for implementing the protocol, its impact on border communities and trade relations, and the extent to which it addresses or exacerbates cross-border security challenges. The study adopted the mixed research method of data analysis, using content analysis to analyze qualitative data, while using simple percentages and tables to analyze numeric data. It relied heavily on secondary sources such as books, journals, articles, periodical, government reports and publications, magazines, unpublished manuscript, and conference papers; also on primary sources such as interviews and questionnaires. Findings reveal that while the protocol has enhanced regional trade and labor mobility, its implementation in Nigeria is undermined by weak institutional capacity, porous borders, lack of legal harmonization, and inadequate security infrastructure. As a result, the protocol has been exploited by criminal elements, facilitating smuggling, human trafficking, and the movement of insurgents. The study identifies five core issues: inconsistent enforcement, economic disparity, persistent security threats, legal misalignment, and limited regional cooperation. Key recommendations include strengthening border surveillance, harmonizing legal frameworks, enhancing regional intelligence-sharing, improving inter-agency coordination, and engaging border communities in security efforts. Overall, the study concludes that while the ECOWAS protocol holds substantial promise for economic integration, its success in Nigeria hinges on a strategic and security-conscious implementation model that aligns with regional integration goals and national priorities.

Keywords: ECOWAS Protocol, Free Movement of Persons and Goods, Regional Integration, Trans-border security, Trade

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

Free movement, as conceptualised in regional integration discourses, refers to the ability of goods, services, and persons to traverse national boundaries with minimal legal or

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logistical impediments. It is a mechanism designed to eliminate barriers to trade and foster interconnectedness within regions. Goods encompass tangible commodities traded between nations, while the free movement of persons relates to the ability of individuals to migrate for purposes such as employment, education, or family reunification without undue restrictions (De Lombaerde et. al., 2010). Trans-border security, on the other hand, involves the safeguarding of national and regional borders against threats such as terrorism, human trafficking, and illicit trade. It is a multidimensional concept encompassing physical, economic, and political security (Buzan, Waever and De-Wilde, 1998). The balance between fostering economic integration through free movement and addressing trans-border security concerns is therefore, both a policy imperative and a theoretical challenge, particularly in regions marked by porous borders and diverse security risks.

Globally and regionally, the discourse on free movement and trans-border security remains pertinent as nations grapple with balancing integration and sovereignty. For instance, the European Union's Schengen Agreement, a similar free movement framework, has faced challenges in addressing security threats while maintaining open borders, particularly during the migration crisis of 2015–2016 (Furst, 2024). In the context of West Africa, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons, established in 1979, stands as a landmark legal framework. This protocol seeks to promote regional integration and economic development by enabling the seamless flow of goods and people across member states (Agyei and Clotey, 2019). According to the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa [UNECA] (2023), intra-ECOWAS trade accounted for approximately 15 per cent of total trade within the bloc. While the region remains heavily reliant on external trade, the protocol's success in facilitating cross-border movement has bolstered regional trade and labour mobility (Adepoju, 2023). However, West Africa's porous borders, coupled with weak institutional capacities, have made the region vulnerable to trans-border crimes such as terrorism, smuggling, and human trafficking. For example, the Sahel region alone has witnessed a surge in terrorist activities, with over 4,000 fatalities reported in 2022 due to cross-border insurgencies (Global Terrorism Index, 2023). This duality underscores the urgent need to interrogate the implications of the ECOWAS Protocol on regional security.

The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons further represents a landmark effort in regional integration, aimed at fostering economic collaboration, social cohesion, and development across West Africa (Trémolières, 2009). The Protocol seeks to eliminate barriers to the movement of people, goods, and services within the ECOWAS sub-region, encapsulating the ideals of collective prosperity and shared security. Its fundamental principles resonate with the broader goals of economic integration, as enshrined in Article 59 of the Revised Treaty of ECOWAS (1993), and align with global aspirations for regional cooperation (Garba and Yeboah, 2022). Despite its potentials, the Protocol's implementation has been allegedly fraught with challenges, especially concerning trans-border security, which remains a pressing concern for member states, particularly Nigeria.

The porous nature of borders in West Africa exacerbates these issues, creating vulnerabilities that are exploited by transnational criminal networks and insurgent groups like Boko Haram and al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) (Aminu and Assel, 2021). In Nigeria, the challenges are particularly acute, given its geographical centrality, population size, and extensive borders that span over 4,000 kilometers. Border communities often become flashpoints for illicit trade, terrorism, and communal conflicts, undermining the intended benefits of the Protocol (Gana, Adamu and Zakariya'u, 2023).

Nigeria's strategic role in ECOWAS further underscores its importance in the discourse on free movement and trans-border security. As the largest economy and most

populous nation in the sub-region, Nigeria wields significant influence in shaping ECOWAS policies and priorities. Its borders serve as critical conduits for regional trade, hosting key entry and exit points such as Seme Border with Benin and Jibiya Border with Niger Republic (Aminu, 2022). However, these same borders are also hotspots for security breaches, highlighting the dual-edged nature of the Protocol's implementation. Oshewolo (2023) and Temitope (2024) posited that Nigeria's leadership role in ECOWAS is pivotal but also burdensome, as the country grapples with balancing its economic integration commitments with national security imperatives.

Despite its significance, the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons' implementation is hindered by numerous policy and operational gaps. Weak governance structures, inadequate border management, and limited cooperation among member states have also undermined its effectiveness. For instance, ECOWAS lacks a robust monitoring mechanism to ensure compliance with the Protocol, while individual states often prioritize national interests over regional commitments (Adamu and Dauda, 2024). In Nigeria, enforcement is further complicated by corruption, insufficient infrastructure, and a lack of coordination among security agencies (Idenyi, Adadu and Baban'numaa, 2023). These gaps not only impede the Protocol's objectives but also exacerbate security risks, calling for urgent policy interventions.

Research Questions

Based on the problem stated above, the study will examine the following research questions:

- i. To what extent has the enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons impacted on the curtailment of trans-border security threats in Nigeria from 2011 – 2023?
- ii. What are the challenges associated with the enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol towards enhancing the trans-border security dynamics in Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to assess the implications of the enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons on trans-border security in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the extent to which the enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons has impacted on the curtailment of trans-border security threats in Nigeria from 2011 – 2023.
- ii. Examine the challenges associated with the enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol towards enhancing the trans-border security dynamics in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons

The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons refers to an agreement among Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) member countries aimed at facilitating the unhindered movement of people, goods, and services across borders within the region (ECOWAS, 1979; Adepaju, 2014). The protocol's primary objective is to promote regional integration, economic cooperation, and development by eliminating barriers to trade and mobility. By reason of this protocol, goods can move freely between ECOWAS member states without tariffs or restrictions, fostering inter-regional trade and economic growth; Citizens of ECOWAS member states are also allowed to travel, reside,

and work within the region without visas, with the ultimate goal of a unified labor market and broader regional cooperation.

According to Olayiwola (2017) the ECOWAS Protocol aims to create a single economic space, promoting free trade and reducing trade costs among member states. In this view, the protocol offers significant opportunities for regional integration, increasing cross-border trade and allowing for a more efficient allocation of resources. However, challenges such as uneven infrastructure, corruption, and trade imbalances remain major obstacles to the full realization of these benefits (Ajayi, 2020). This researcher observed that there is need to adequately contextualize these challenges based on the background they may be emanating from since not all challenges in point A may necessarily be a concern in point B, hence there was need for localized examples.

Studies like Balogun & Adeyemo (2019) suggest that while the free movement of goods has led to positive economic outcomes in some countries, others have struggled with the effective implementation due to domestic policy constraints and national security concerns. This entails that the implementation of the protocol has produced mixed results due to the intervening policies or national security concerns.

Concept of Trans-Border Security

Trans-border security refers to the measures and mechanisms that states employ to monitor, regulate, and protect their borders against cross-border threats such as terrorism, smuggling, human trafficking, arms proliferation, and illegal migration (Andreas, 2003). This State-Centric perspective views borders as zones of national vulnerability requiring strong state control. This author presents borders as critical points for national security enforcement. However, critics argue that this framing overemphasizes militarized and surveillance-based approaches while neglecting the socio-economic drivers of cross-border movement and the human costs of rigid enforcement (Mountz, 2010).

On his part, Williams (2008) in his Regional Security Framework approach defined Trans-border security as also encompassing collaborative regional efforts where neighboring states share intelligence, coordinate border patrols, and harmonize policies to combat transnational security threats. It reflects the interdependence of states within geopolitical regions, such as ECOWAS or the EU. This authors' definition underscores the importance of regional integration in addressing trans-border security challenges. This aligns with practical efforts by regional blocs like ECOWAS and the EU, which have created frameworks for collective action. However, cooperation is often undermined by unequal capacity among states, lack of trust, and divergent political agendas.

Newman (2001) defined trans-border security from a human security perspective, arguing that trans-border security includes ensuring the safety and dignity of individuals crossing borders, especially refugees, migrants, and displaced persons. It calls for balancing security concerns with humanitarian principles. While the human security approach (Newman, 2001) expands the concept to include humanitarian concerns, critics point out its operational ambiguity. Balancing the protection of individuals with national interests often leads to tension, particularly when states prioritize sovereignty over humanitarian access.

Theoretical Framework

Border Regimes Theory

The BRT was propounded by Sandro Mezzadra and Brett Neilson in 2001. It offers a critical framework for understanding the complex dynamics of border control and migration management. The Theory posits that contemporary border regimes are characterised by a set of interconnected practices and policies that aim to regulate the movement of people, goods, and ideas across borders (Favell, 2022). The Theory also highlights the role of power

dynamics in shaping border regimes. As such, the BRT views the actions of BS agencies and other security institutions as an exercise of power to control and regulate the border region, not just to prevent physical infiltration but also to assert authority and legitimacy over the territory (Haas, 2021).

The BRT was however criticised for its tendency to oversimplify complex border dynamics by focusing primarily on state-centric approaches. Additionally, critics argue that the theory often neglects the agency of border communities. It also disregards the ways in which they actively shape and contest border regimes, which is vital for effective implementation of ECOWAS free movement policy (Adesina, 2021). Notwithstanding, the Theory has been acknowledged to provide valuable insights into the complexities of ECOWAS free movement policy and trans-border security.

In the context of this study, the BRT emphasises that the ECOWAS operates within a complex web of border regimes, where traditional notions of sovereignty and territorial integrity intersect with transnational threats. In Nigeria, porous borders with neighbouring countries such as Niger, Chad, and Cameroon exacerbate the challenges of insurgent infiltration and cross-border criminal activities posing threats to trans-border security. Furthermore, the Theory emphasises the importance of cooperation and coordination between Nigeria and immediate neighbours, as well as with ECOWAS and other regional organisations like the LCBC, to secure Nigerian borders while ensuring the implementation of the ECOWAS policy of free movement of Goods and persons. Evidently, the BRT offers valuable insights into the complexities of ECOWAS policy under investigation and trans-border border security in Nigeria and therefore adopted as a guide in this study.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed-method research design, allowing for comprehensive data collection from natural settings. The research seeks to evaluate the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons and its implications for trans-border security in West Africa, focusing on Nigeria between 2013 and 2023. The interplay between the protocol's implementation and trans-border security dynamics is therefore critically examined

For this study, a total population of 75,393 was adopted as the study population as obtained from divers' sources, the target population is categorized as follows: Representatives of ECOWAS; as well as officials of the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS), Nigeria Customs Service (NCS) and Nigeria Police Force (NPF) – Border Patrol Unit (BPU). To determine the appropriate sample size, the study employed Yammane's (1967) formula, a widely recognized method in social sciences, which provides a systematic approach to achieving a representative and statistically reliable sample approximately 400. The sampling techniques employed in this study are purposive and stratified sampling, both of which play critical roles in ensuring the relevance, effectiveness of the data collection process. Aligned with the study objectives, the researcher intends to gather comprehensive qualitative data to examine the dynamics of ECOWAS protocols and their intersection with trans-border security challenges. Data collection involved interviews with policymakers and security experts, as well as reviews of official documents and regional policy frameworks.

The data collected for the study utilized a mixed-methods' approach to ensure comprehensive analysis. Descriptive statistics, including tables, simple percentages, and graphical representations such as bar and pie charts, was employed to analyze quantitative data obtained through questionnaires.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Extent that Enforcement of ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement impacted on the curtailing of Trans-border Security Threats in Nigeria

The interviewed respondents have basically argued that the extent to which the enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons and Goods has impacted the curtailing of trans-border security threats in Nigeria is mixed and complex, showing both positive and negative outcomes. While the protocol was designed to promote regional integration, trade, and mobility, its enforcement has had limited success in addressing security threats, and in some cases, it has exacerbated vulnerabilities. For instance, **Respondent 1** in this interview reacted thus:

*More often than not limited enforcement of the ECOWAS free movement Protocol weakens Security Outcomes and security measures have themselves sometimes undermined the Protocol. Porous borders and inconsistent enforcement of the protocol have made Nigeria's borders vulnerable to infiltration by armed groups, smugglers, and traffickers. The lack of biometric registration and identity tracking systems across the region hampers real-time monitoring of cross-border movements (**Respondent 1**, Officer of the Nigerian police Force Border Patrol Unit, interviewed 11th June, 2025).*

Similarly, **Respondent 2** have stated the following:

*The issue of the growing insecurity across the Nigerian borders is sometimes not a function of the protocol alone, many border officials are either undertrained or under-resourced, making it difficult to balance facilitation of legal movement with effective security screening leading to influx of criminals and heightened crime proliferations across the Nigerian borders. In reaction to rising transnational crimes and terrorism, Nigeria has frequently suspended parts of the protocol, including the 2019–2020 land border closure which was aimed at combating smuggling and arms trafficking. These unilateral actions demonstrate the tensions between security concerns and regional mobility commitments under the ECOWAS framework (**Respondent 2**, Officer of the Nigerian Custom Service, interviewed 10th June, 2025).*

Conversely, other respondents had praised the enforcement of the protocol arguing that it has led to at least partial success in regional collaborations and that existent security threats have always emanated where the protocol has been abused in one way or the other. **Respondent 3**, argued thus:

The protocol has contributed to improved intelligence sharing and joint patrols, particularly under ECOWAS security initiatives such as the West African Police Information System (WAPIS) and the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF) for the Lake Chad region. However, coordination remains weak, and there is limited interoperability between Nigeria's security agencies and those of neighboring countries. More so, non-

state actors and criminal networks exploit the protocol's provisions to move illicit arms, drugs, and fighters across borders disguised as ECOWAS citizens. The failure to fully implement border control mechanisms, such as biometric data capture, means that dangerous individuals often cross borders undetected leading to a struggle by Nigeria to balance regional obligations under ECOWAS with its domestic security priorities. As a result, enforcement of the protocol is sometimes selective, with stricter measures applied in volatile regions (e.g., Northeast and Northwest), limiting the protocol's effectiveness in creating a unified regional security front (**Respondent 3**, ECOWAS Trade and Security Expert, interviewed 24th June, 2025).

Table 1: Extent of Impacts that Enforcement of ECOWAS free movement Protocol has brought on Trans-border Security in Nigeria

Extent of Impact	Numeric Value of Response	Frequency		Remark
No Significant Extent	1	16	16	The Enforcement of ECOWAS free movement Protocol on persons and goods has brought a Significant level of Impact on Trans-border Security in Nigeria.
Less Significant Extent	2	36	72	
Undecided/Neutral	3	25	75	
Significant Extent	4	153	612	
Very Significant Extent	5	165	825	
Total		395	1,600	Result = 4.0

Source: Field Survey, June, 2025

The table above weighed the extent of impacts that the ECOWAS protocol on free movement of persons and goods has brought on trans-border security in Nigeria. About 16 respondents were of the view that the protocol has exerted no significant level of impact on trans-border security in Nigeria.

Similarly, 36 respondents were of the view that the level of impact wielded by the protocol on trans-border security remains less significant, 25 respondents stand undecided when about 153 respondents were of the view that the level of impact exerted by the free movement protocol on trans-border security in Nigeria was Significant.

Meanwhile, 165 respondents believe the level of impact that the ECOWAS free movement protocol wields on trans-border security in Nigeria is nothing short of being very significant.

At the end, the researcher used the 5 point Likert scale to weigh the opinions and the result returned **4.0** aligning with the numeric value of the fourth opinion. The implication of this is that Enforcement of ECOWAS free movement Protocol on persons and goods has brought a significant level of Impact on Trans-border Security in Nigeria. And it further entails that if the situation must not escalate appropriate measures needed to be taken to address the spade of insecurity and crime emanating from enforcement of the ECOWAS free movement protocol on Nigeria territory.

The implementation of ECOWAS free movement Protocol on persons and goods has brought a significant level of Impact on Trans-border Security in Nigeria. The broad analysis of responses from interview sources demonstrates a limited overall Positive impact of the protocol. While the ECOWAS Protocol aims to promote peace and cooperation, the weak

enforcement mechanisms, coupled with security challenges unique to Nigeria, mean that it has only marginally contributed to curtailing trans-border threats. In fact, gaps in enforcement have often created security loopholes exploited by non-state actors. By and Large, after considering the above arguments it reveals that the extent to which the enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons and Goods has impacted the curtailing of trans-border security threats in Nigeria is mixed and complex, showing both positive and negative outcomes. While the protocol was designed to promote regional integration, trade, and mobility, its enforcement has had limited success in addressing security threats, and in some cases, it has exacerbated vulnerabilities.

Secondary literatures also corroborated the fact that the ECOWAS Protocol has facilitated increased cross-border trade, leading to economic benefits for border communities but also attract criminality to Nigeria borders when appropriate security measures are lacking. For instance, studies like Olabanji & Omoyibo (2020) and Abidemi & Yakubu (2022) have shown that the protocol has contributed to the growth of intra-regional trade and investment within the sub-region. However, the implementation of the protocol has also presented challenges. This study highlighted that despite the protocol's provisions, there are still significant barriers to the free movement of people and goods in the region, such as inadequate infrastructure, worsening trans-border security and bureaucratic bottlenecks.

Challenges Associated with Enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Enhancement of Trans-border security in Nigeria

In spite of some of the benefits emanating from the ECOWAS free movement protocol, interviewed respondents points out that the protocol and of course the concern of curtailing trans-border security have been slowed down by significant hindrances such as inadequate funding, lack of modern equipment, awareness of Protocol Provisions, challenges with Border Crossings, Corruption and Extortion amongst others. **Respondent 4** in this interview, maintained thus:

*Reports of harassment, extortion, and delays at border points were common, often attributed to corrupt practices by some officials. However, the growing issue of Banditry, insurgency and trafficking in places like Katsina-Jibiya and Ilesa-Konni have complicated the enforcement of the free movement protocol as border personnel often face threats from criminal elements, making enforcement risky and challenging. But there is a need for greater involvement of local communities in surveillance and reporting to enhance security (**Respondent 4**, a Member of border community, interviewed 24th June, 2025).*

Like the above Respondent, other respondents equally shared similar security and other related concerns. **Respondent 5** stated thus:

Cross-border crimes such as smuggling, trafficking and insurgency often lead to stricter border controls, which contradict the protocol's liberal goals. Terrorism and banditry, particularly in northern border regions, compel authorities to tighten movements and even temporarily close borders. Criminal elements exploit the free movement clause to enter Nigeria illegally or transport contraband goods, while some migrants overstay beyond the allowed 90 days without proper documentation. But by and large, strict or inconsistent enforcement of the protocol of free movement negatively

affected cross-border trade, which is vital for the economic well-being of these communities (Respondent 5, Representative of the Ministry Foreign Affairs, interviewed 10th July, 2025).

For **Respondent 6**, in his words:

Limited deployment of technological tools for surveillance and data collection hampers monitoring and enforcement. This is as many Nigerian borders lack modern facilities for customs and immigration processing, leading to delays and corruption. That said, the issue of bribery and harassment by border officials discourage free movement and trade. ECOWAS citizens often face illegal fees and demands for travel documents not required under the protocol (Respondent 6, Official of the Nigerian Custom Service, interviewed 24th July, 2025).

Similarly, **Respondent 7**, argued around the issue of lack of Synergy by security bodies attached to the borders. He stated thus:

Poor synergy among national agencies (NIS, NCS and the Nigerian Police) and between Nigeria and neighboring countries affects consistent protocol enforcement. More so, is the issue of overlapping mandates and lack of standardized procedures leading to confusion and inefficiencies in the implementation of the free movement protocol with attendant security issues (Respondent 7, Official of the International organization for Migration, interviewed 12th July, 2025).

Finally, **Respondent 8** dwelt on the issue of lack of awareness of the provisions of the protocol and the issue of lack of data on migration flows and goods movement. She stated that:

Many ECOWAS citizens and even some officials are not fully informed about the rights and obligations under the protocol leading to arbitrary restrictions and wrongful denial of entry or transit, closely related to this is the issue of lack of data on migration flows and goods movement which also limits evidence-based policymaking. Besides, ECOWAS has demonstrated limited capacity to monitor compliance or enforce sanctions on member states that violate the protocol. These and many more seems to weaken the enforcement of ECOWAS free movement protocol as much as it disrupt and give rise to trans-border security concerns across Nigerian borders (Respondent 8, Member of Border Community, interviewed 24th July, 2025).

Table 2: Challenges Associated with Enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Enhancement of Trans-border security in Nigeria

S/N	Theme four: Weighing the Challenges Associated with Enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Enhancement of Trans- border security in Nigeria	Numerical Value/ Code of Responses					Performance/Remark
		SD 1	D 2	N 3	A 4	SA 5	
1	Inadequate border security infrastructure funding is an issue that is capable of slowing down enforcement of the free movement protocol and hampering security efficiency.	16	23	19	183	154	Impact of Challenge: significant impact
	Total	16	46	57	732	770	Numeric Significance: 4.1 Agreed
2	Lack of modern equipment is an issue that is capable of slowing down enforcement of the free movement protocol and hampering border security effectiveness.	21	33	30	148	163	Impact of Challenge: significant impact
	Total	21	66	90	592	815	Numeric Significance: 4.0 Agreed
3	Awareness of the Protocol Provisions is an issue that is capable of slowing down enforcement of the free movement protocol and hampering security collaborations.	50	56	41	104	144	Impact of Challenge: Relative significant impact
	Total	50	112	123	416	720	Numeric Significance = 3.5 Neutral/ Undecided
4	Border Crossings challenge is one of the notable challenges orchestrated by Nigerian attempt to curb its growing insecurity around border regions by suspending some aspect of the protocol.	34	45	12	127	177	Impact of Challenge: significant negative impact
	Total	34	90	66	508	885	Numeric Significance = 4.0 Agreed
5	The issue of bribery and harassment by border officials discourage free movement and trade	14	15	4	196	166	Impact of Challenge : significant negative impact

	thereby hampering the enforcement of the free movement protocol.						
	Total	14	45	12	784	830	Numeric Significance = 4.2 Agreed
6	Issue of using insecurity as a decoy by criminal elements to enter Nigeria illegally or transport contraband goods is a challenge slowing down the enforcement of the protocol and curbing insecurity in within Nigerian borders.	16	10	10	154	205	Impact of Challenge: significant negative impact
	Total	16	20	30	616	1,025	Numeric Significance = 4.3 Agreed

Source: Field Survey, July, 2025

NB: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

The table above reveals the challenges that seem to weaken the enforcement of the ECOWAS free movement protocol as well as weakening the approaches directed at strengthening trans-border security in Nigeria. The table in the first question showed that respondent agreed to the assertion that inadequate border security infrastructure funding is an issue that is capable of slowing down enforcement of the free movement protocol and hampering security efficiency at 4.1 numeric significance. This implied that it had a significant impact.

Secondly, the survey showed that respondent agreed to the assertion that lack of modern equipment is an issue that is capable of slowing down enforcement of the free movement protocol and hampering border security effectiveness at 4.0 numeric significance. This implied that it also had a significant impact.

Thirdly, the survey showed that respondent were Neutral or undecided to the assertion that Awareness of the Protocol Provisions is an issue that is capable of slowing down enforcement of the free movement protocol and hampering security collaborations at 3.5 numeric significance. This implied that it had a relatively significant impact.

Similarly, the fourth survey showed that respondent agreed to the assertion that Border Crossings challenge is one of the notable challenge orchestrated by Nigerian attempt to curb its growing insecurity around border regions by suspending some aspect of the protocol at 4.0 numeric significance. This implied that it had a significant negative impact.

In the fifth survey the respondent agreed to the assertion that the issue of bribery and harassment by border officials discourage free movement and trade thereby hampering the enforcement of the free movement protocol at 4.2 numeric significance. This implied that it also had a significant negative impact.

In the final survey respondents agreed to the assertion that issue of using insecurity as a decoy by criminal elements to enter Nigeria illegally or transport contraband goods is a challenge slowing down the enforcement of the protocol and curbing insecurity within Nigerian borders at 4.3 numeric significance. This implied that it also had a significant impact.

The broad implication after observing data collected revealed that enforcement of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement within Nigerian borders involved a combination of inter-agency collaboration, technological tools, and community engagement but this did not

come without attendant implications and challenges. However, challenges such as inadequate resources, corruption, and security threats hinder effective implementation. Addressing these issues requires comprehensive strategies, including capacity building, infrastructural development, and stronger community partnerships.

Some of these facts were corroborated in literatures like Olabanji & Omoyibo (2020) and Adewale (2020) cited that security concerns and cross-border crimes often hampered implementation of the free movement protocol. The Nigerian government often prioritizes national security over regional integration due to threats like insurgency, trafficking, and arms smuggling. These threats have led to temporary border closures and tighter surveillance, undermining the protocol. More so, studies like Olayemi (2019) and Ukaoha (2018) also argued that corruption and administrative inefficiencies delays the implementation of the free movement protocol. Officials at border posts frequently demand illegal fees or extort travelers and traders, creating a barrier to the free movement guaranteed under the ECOWAS Protocol. Similarly, Abidemi & Yakubu (2022) upheld that poor border Infrastructure and Technology Deficit impacted on the implementation of the ECOWAS free movement Protocol. Also substantiating that inadequate facilities, lack of biometric systems and insufficient staffing at many Nigerian borders hamper efficient protocol implementation.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The study concludes that the enforcement of the ECOWAS Free Movement Protocol in Nigeria presents a paradox: it offers promising economic benefits through improved trade and labor mobility, yet simultaneously exposes the country to heightened trans-border security threats. The lack of harmonization between national laws and regional frameworks, weak institutional capacity and infrastructural decay have impeded effective protocol implementation. Without deliberate reforms and coordinated regional efforts, the full potential of the ECOWAS protocol cannot be realized. The study emphasizes the need for strategic reforms to align security priorities with regional mobility objectives. Therefore, a balanced approach that prioritizes both regional integration and national security is critical.

Recommendations

- 1 The federal government should harmonize national security laws with ECOWAS protocols by revising Nigeria's immigration, customs, and border security laws to align with ECOWAS free movement objectives, thereby reducing policy contradictions and enforcement gaps.
- 2 Promotion of regional intelligence and security collaboration by establishing joint border security task forces, intelligence-sharing platforms, and regular bilateral/multilateral operations with neighbouring ECOWAS states to address cross-border crimes.

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